

Real Steps to Support Innovation Activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: *The article summarizes the real steps to support the innovative activities of small business structures, providing them with unused production areas and equipment. Particular attention is paid to the issues of integrating research institutes and higher education institutions with knowledge-intensive industries. It is noted that integration should involve the unification of human and other resources in conjunction with the timing of entry into the global dynamics of scientific and technological development.*

Keywords: *stimulation, entrepreneurship, activation, innovative infrastructure, innovative entrepreneurship, small business, intellectual property.*

The Decree of the President of the Republic approved the Program of State Support for Entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which provided for tax incentives for innovative activities of entrepreneurs, but it turned out that this was not taken into account in the Tax Code (1998).

Back in March 1996, a very important document was adopted by four governments. By the Resolution of the Interparliamentary Committee of the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic and the Russian Federation, a model Law "On Innovations" was adopted, which defined the content and nature of the actions of the states - parties to the Treaty, with the aim of organizing and activating innovation activities as a strategic direction that ensures the reduction of the gap in the socio-economic development of these countries and countries with an established market economy. Although this law was not adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan, it gave impetus to making decisions on activating innovation activities, which today has led to the creation of a regulatory framework in the innovation and scientific and technical spheres, innovation infrastructure, attracting capital to the innovation sphere, and the formation of innovative entrepreneurship in the above-mentioned CIS countries.

In June 1997, at a plenary session of the CIS Interparliamentary Assembly, a model Law "On the Innovation and Investment Network Infrastructure" was adopted, i.e. a system of interacting organizations and management units that ensures the resolution of issues related to the activation of innovation activities.

In the period 1992-1997, the Republic of Uzbekistan for the first time set the goals and principles of state regulation of innovation activities, the provisions of the National Innovation Policy, adopted the state innovation doctrine, defined laws, and the goals of state innovation programs. However, the "Innovation Code" was not adopted.

In Uzbekistan, in 1997-2004, the regulatory and legislative framework for supporting small businesses was improved, which served to activate its development. In addition to general measures to support small businesses, the Government developed a Program for the Development of Small Business in the Scientific and Technological Sphere, in accordance with which the following measures were implemented:

- creation of small business structures;
- provision of unused production space and equipment to small businesses;
- formation of a market for high-tech products.

However, at that time, due to the lack of sufficient funding and an appropriate regulatory framework, the formation of the innovation sphere in the republic was sporadic.

The Law “On State Support for Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship” was adopted, designed to stimulate the activities of small business structures.

A program for the integration of research institutes and higher education institutions with knowledge-intensive industries was developed. Integration involves the unification of human and other resources in a timely manner linked to the timing of entry into the global dynamics of scientific and technological development.

The Government adopted a program of innovative activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which laid the foundation for the creation of conditions for the innovative development of the country.

Real steps of state support for innovative activities.

One of the real steps of the state to support innovative activities in the Republic was the adoption in 2018 for the next 10 years of the concept of scientific and scientific-technical policy aimed at ensuring stable development of the scientific and technical sphere, the formation of scientific and technical potential that meets modern requirements for innovative development of the economy and its resource capabilities, ensuring the creation of a competitive national economy and its sustainable development. In 2018, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovations" was adopted. This document laid the foundations for the transition of the country's economy to an innovative path of development and provides for measures for state support of innovative activities in the field of science and technology, state participation in the development of innovative infrastructure and personnel training. To achieve the goals set by the concept of scientific and technical development, the following measures were taken: development of a regulatory framework in the innovative, scientific and technical sphere, resource provision, including financial support for scientific, technical, innovative activities.

In May 2021, the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the Innovative Development Program for 2022-2025 by its Resolution. The goal of the program is to create the necessary conditions and a favorable environment for the development of the country's economy based on the use of scientific and technological achievements, the formation of a balanced production infrastructure and the gradual replacement of part of the raw materials component in GDP with high-tech export products. The program addresses the following tasks:

- ensuring priority scientific, technical and technological development of the economy;
- formation of non-resource sectors of the economy;
- formation of a system of state support for innovative activities and the preferential development of industrial entrepreneurial activities;
- carrying out technological modernization of industry and creation of export-oriented knowledge-intensive industries;
- formation of infrastructure for innovative activities;
- attracting small businesses to the innovation sphere;
- staffing for innovation activities;

- formation of a regulatory framework for innovative activities that ensures the priority of innovative development of the economy;
- development of international scientific and technical cooperation.

The activation of state regulation does not diminish the importance of market self-organization, does not replace entrepreneurial initiative, but, on the contrary, creates conditions for their progress.

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